

Navier Stokes in Higher Order Dual Numbers and Other Algebraic Systems

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Abstract

The Navier-Stokes Equation needs no introduction. In this paper we define an Infinitely Adjoined Algebra and we rewrite the Navier-Stokes Equation in this new Algebra and observe that the Equation is well preserved except for a new constant. The paper was written as an encouragement to draw similarities hyperreals and dual numbers ,and as evidence that studying infinitely adjoined algebras could be useful

The Navier-Stokes equation is a notoriously nonlinear PDE. We aim to explore higher-dimensional algebras, particularly to observe what happens as we move towards infinite-dimensional algebras.

Introduction

A PDE is defined as an equation of the form:

$$F(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, u, \frac{\partial u}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial u}{\partial x_n}, \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}, \dots) = 0$$

Some examples include:

- Heat Equation:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \alpha \nabla^2 u$$

- Wave Equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u$$

- Navier-Stokes Equation:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + (\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u} = -\nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{u}$$

Algebras and Adjoined Algebras

An algebra A over a field K is a vector space with a bilinear operation:

$$A \times A \rightarrow A$$

Axioms:

- $(a + b)c = ac + bc$
- $a(b + c) = ab + ac$
- $\lambda(ab) = (\lambda a)b = a(\lambda b)$

We form adjoined algebras as follows:

$$F[x]/(p(x)) = F[m], \quad \text{where } p(m) = 0$$

These are standard Some examples of Adjoined Algebras include:

- $\mathbb{R}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$ - Complex Numbers
- $\mathbb{R}[x]/(x^2)$ - Dual Numbers
- $\mathbb{R}[x]/(x^2 - 1)$ - Split Complex Numbers

Infinite Order Algebras

We define infinite order algebras as limits:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{R}[x]/(x^n) \quad (\text{Infinite Order Dual Numbers})$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{R}[x]/(x^n + 1) \quad (\text{Infinite Order Complex Numbers})$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{R}[x]/(x^n - 1) \quad (\text{Infinite Order Split Complex Numbers})$$

Function Definitions

For functions in infinite order algebras:

$$f : \mathbb{R}^{(\infty)} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(\infty)}$$

$$f = f_0 + f_1\epsilon + f_2\epsilon^2 + f_3\epsilon^3 + \dots, \quad f_j \rightarrow f_\infty$$

For complex infinite order algebras:

$$f = f_0 + f_1i + f_2i^2 + f_3i^3 + \dots, \quad f_j \rightarrow f_\infty$$

For split complex infinite order algebras:

$$f = f_0 + f_1j + f_2j^2 + f_3j^3 + \dots, \quad f_j \rightarrow f_\infty$$

Results

a) Dual Number Series

$$S = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \epsilon^n = \frac{1}{1 - \epsilon}$$

b) Complex Number Series

$$S = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} i^n = \frac{1+i}{1-i}$$

c) Split-Complex Number Series

$$S = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} j^n = 1$$

Looking for differences in PDEs in infinite dimensional algebras.

so an interesting thing to observe is what happens to these PDEs in D_∞ as the non linearity in the PDE is completely removed transformed into something algebraic?

We also explore what happens in C_∞ and C_∞^s

Heat Equation in $D_\infty, C_\infty, C_\infty^s$

let the function $u = u_0 + u_1\epsilon + u_2\epsilon^2 \dots - u_\infty\epsilon^\infty$ then in the Heat equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t}\epsilon + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t}\epsilon^2 \dots - \frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t}\epsilon^\infty$$

and

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2} + \epsilon \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x^2} \dots - \epsilon^\infty \frac{\partial^2 u_\infty}{\partial x^2}$$

by equating the ϵ^k parts,

we get heat equation for each component of \vec{u} u_0 to u_∞

$$\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2}$$

⋮

$$\frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 u_\infty}{\partial x^2}$$

We get the same implications by comparing and equating the i^k parts and j^k parts in C_∞ and C_∞^s respectively.

Burger PDE in $D_\infty, C_\infty, C_\infty^s$

a) Burgers PDE in D_∞

Given by

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

$$u = u_0 + u_1 \epsilon + u_2 \epsilon^2 \dots u_\infty \epsilon^\infty$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} \epsilon + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t} \epsilon^2 \dots \frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t} \epsilon^\infty$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = (u_0 + u_1 \epsilon + u_2 \epsilon^2 \dots u_\infty \epsilon^\infty) \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} \epsilon + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x} \epsilon^2 \dots \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n u_i \epsilon^i \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x} \epsilon^j \right)$$

and we know that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^n b_j x^j \right) &= \sum_{k=0}^{2n} c_k x^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n} c_k x^k \end{aligned}$$

we know

$$\begin{aligned} c_k^p &= \sum_{i=0}^k a_i b_{k-i} u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n c_k \epsilon^k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n} c_k \epsilon^k \right) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{i=0}^k u_i \frac{\partial u_{k-i}}{\partial x} \right) \epsilon^k \end{aligned}$$

if $u_i = u_0, \forall i$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{u} \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial x} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{i=0}^k u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \right) \epsilon^k \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n (k+1) u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \epsilon^k \\ &= u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n (k+1) \epsilon^k \end{aligned}$$

what is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n k\epsilon^k$?

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= 0 + \epsilon + 2\epsilon^2 + 3\epsilon^3 \dots \infty\epsilon^\infty \\
 S\epsilon &= 0 + \epsilon^2 + 2\epsilon^3 \dots (\infty - 1)\epsilon^\infty + \epsilon^{\infty+1} \\
 (S - S\epsilon) &= 0 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 + \epsilon^3 \dots \infty + 1 = S \\
 S(1 - \epsilon) &= \frac{1}{1 - \epsilon} - 1 = \frac{1 - (1 - \epsilon)}{1 - \epsilon} = \frac{\epsilon}{1 - \epsilon} \\
 S &= \frac{\epsilon}{(1 - \epsilon)^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Giving us

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\epsilon^2}{(1 - \epsilon)^2} u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x}$$

Now lets do the same substitution

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} &= (1 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 - \epsilon^\infty) \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} \\
 \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} &= (1 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 - \epsilon^\infty) \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Burgers Eqn in D_∞ is given by the following.

let $u = (1 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 - \epsilon^\infty)$

and let $u_0 = \frac{1}{1 - \epsilon} u_0$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

converts to

$$(1 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 - \epsilon^\infty) \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{(1 - \epsilon)^2} u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} = (1 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 - \epsilon^\infty) \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2}$$

giving

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{1 - \epsilon} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{(1 - \epsilon)^2} u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} &= \frac{1}{1 - \epsilon} \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2} \\
 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{1 - \epsilon} u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} &= \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

0.1 b) Doing the same in C_∞

Letting

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= u_0 + iu_1 + i^2u_2 + i^3u_3 \cdots + i^\infty u_\infty \\
 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + i \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} + i^2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t} \cdots + i^\infty \frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t} \\
 \\
 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} &= \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2} + i \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2} + i^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x^2} \cdots \\
 u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n u_i i^i \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x} i^j \right) \\
 &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{i=0}^k u_i \frac{\partial u_{k-i}}{\partial x} \right) i^k \right) \\
 &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^k u_i \frac{\partial u_{k-i}}{\partial x} \right) i^k + \left(\sum_{i=0}^n u_i \frac{\partial u_{n-i}}{\partial x} \right) i^n \right) \\
 &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{i=0}^k u_i \frac{\partial u_{k-i}}{\partial x} \right) i^k - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^k u_i \frac{\partial u_{k-i}}{\partial x} \right) i^{k+n} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

if we say $u_i = u, \forall i$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (k+1) u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} i^k \right) \\
 &= u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n (k+1) i^k \\
 &= u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} (1 \cdot 0 + 2 \cdot i + 3 \cdot i^2 + 4 \cdot i^3 \cdots + (\infty + 1) i^\infty) \\
 &\Rightarrow u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} (0 + i - 2 - 3i \cdots + (\infty + 1) + i\infty) \\
 &\Rightarrow u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} (0 + i(1 - \infty) - 2(1 - \infty) \dots) \\
 &= u_0 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \left(\infty \times \frac{i+1}{1-i} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

and from \mathbb{C}_∞^s and im sure if evaluated as \mathbb{C}_∞^s would also have some unbounded nature in the form of ∞ or $\frac{1}{(1-\epsilon)^2}$

Now Finally lets see what happens when we take Navier Stokes in D_∞

Navier Stokes in D_∞

Starting with simpler terms

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + (\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u} = -\nabla p + \nu \Delta \vec{u} \vec{u} = u_0 + \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \epsilon^3 u_3, \dots, \epsilon^\infty u_\infty$$

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \epsilon \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t} + \dots + \epsilon^\infty \frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t}$$

$(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}$ is complicated so we leave it for later .

$$\nabla p = \nabla p_1 + \epsilon \nabla p_2 + \epsilon^2 \nabla p_3, \dots, \epsilon^\infty \nabla p_\infty$$

$$\Delta \vec{u} = \Delta u_0 + \epsilon \Delta u_1 + \epsilon^2 \Delta u_2, \dots, \epsilon^\infty \Delta u_\infty$$

now we move to $(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}$

Evaluating $(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}$ in D_∞

to see what happens to the $(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}$ term
in D_∞ lets start in D_2

1) in D_2

$$\epsilon^2 = 0$$

$$\vec{u} = \vec{u}_0 + \epsilon \vec{u}_1$$

$$\vec{u} \cdot \nabla \vec{u} = (\vec{u}_0 + \epsilon \vec{u}_1) \cdot \nabla (\vec{u}_0 + \epsilon \vec{u}_1)$$

$$= (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0 + \epsilon [(\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_1 + (\vec{u}_1 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0]$$

Real Part = $(\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0$

Imaginary part or

ϵ part = $(\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_1 + (\vec{u}_1 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0$

2) in D_3

$$\epsilon^3 = 0$$

$$\vec{u} = \vec{u}_0 + \epsilon \vec{u}_1 + \epsilon^2 \vec{u}_2$$

$$(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u} = (\vec{u}_0 + \epsilon \vec{u}_1 + \epsilon^2 \vec{u}_2) \cdot \nabla (\vec{u}_0 + \epsilon \vec{u}_1 + \epsilon^2 \vec{u}_2)$$

$$= (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0 + \epsilon [(\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_1 + (\vec{u}_1 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0] + \epsilon^2 [(\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_2 + (\vec{u}_1 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_1 + (\vec{u}_2 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0]$$

What can be noticed was the sum of the indices was constant which which were the number of terms for the ϵ^i part

$$N(\epsilon^0) = 1$$

$$N(\epsilon^1) = 2$$

$$N(\epsilon^2) = 3$$

$$N(\epsilon^i) = ?$$

This is because the $(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}$ term expands in the following way

$$(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} = \sum_{i=0}^{2n-2} \epsilon^i \left(\sum_{\substack{j+k=i \\ 0 \leq j, k \leq n-1}} (\vec{u}_j \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}_k \right)$$

now since $\epsilon^i > 0$

$$\epsilon^i = 0$$

$$\text{iff } i \in [0, 2n-2] \cap \mathbb{N}$$

$$(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \epsilon^i \left(\sum_{\substack{j+k=i \\ 0 \leq j, k \leq n-1}} (\vec{u}_j \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}_k \right)$$

When $u_0 = u_j \forall j \in \mathbb{N}$

The ϵ^i part will be $= N(\epsilon^i)(\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}_0$

$$(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} = \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} N(\epsilon^i) \cdot \epsilon^i \right) (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}_0$$

or $(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} = (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}_0 \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} N(\epsilon^i) \times \epsilon^i \right)$

now what is $N(\epsilon^i)$?

$$N(\epsilon^i) = f(i)$$

$$f : \mathbb{N} \longrightarrow \mathbb{N}$$

Such that $f(i)$ is the number of ways

$\exists j, k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $j, k \leq n-1$ and

$$j + k = i$$

now if $i, j, k \leq n-1$

then $f(i) = i + 1$

if $u_i = u_j \forall i, j$ then in D_∞

$$(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} = (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}_0 \times \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (i+1)\epsilon^i \right)$$

Now plugging this all to get a Navier Stokes
in D_∞ gives us (if $u_i = u_j$)

$$\frac{1}{1-\epsilon} \frac{\partial \vec{u}_0}{\partial t} + (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0 (1 + 2\epsilon + 3\epsilon^2 \dots) = -\frac{1}{1-\epsilon} \nabla p_0 + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{u}_0$$

or

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}_0}{\partial t} + (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0 (1 + 2\epsilon + 3\epsilon^2 \dots) (1 - \epsilon) = -\nabla p_0 + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{u}_0$$

now what is $(1 - \epsilon)(1 + 2\epsilon + 3\epsilon^2 \dots)$

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 + 2\epsilon + 3\epsilon^2 + 4\epsilon^3 + 5\epsilon^4 + 6\epsilon^5 \dots + \infty \epsilon^{\infty-1} + \infty \epsilon^\infty \\ & -\epsilon - 2\epsilon^2 - 3\epsilon^3 - 4\epsilon^4 - 5\epsilon^5 - 6\epsilon^6 \dots - \infty \epsilon^\infty \\ & = 1 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2 + \epsilon^3 \dots + \infty \epsilon^{\infty-1} \\ & = \frac{1}{1-\epsilon} \end{aligned}$$

in a strange sense

$$(1 + 2\epsilon + 3\epsilon^2 \dots) = \frac{1}{(1-\epsilon)^2}$$

so in a weird way we have a scalar version of Navier Stokes with a coefficient.

$$\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + (u_0 \cdot \nabla) u_0 \frac{1}{1-\epsilon} = -\nabla p_0 + \nu \nabla u_0$$

or

$$\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + (u_0 \cdot \nabla) u_0 F = -\nabla p_0 + \nu \nabla u_0$$

in this if F is a constant then this is
probably a 1D version of Burgers Equation.

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